

WORK ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN OUR COUNTRY UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: *This article shows the work in the field of foreign languages, which is developing in our country. The problems of linguistics and foreign languages, the work being done on them are described.*

Keywords: *Educator, innovation, education, science, personnel*

The future of our independent Republic depends on the formation of our work as a person with high spirituality, creative thinking and independent learning skills. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirzиеv states that "Uzbekistan must be globally competitive in the field of science, intellectual potential, modern personnel, high technology" [1]. Therefore, one of the most important tasks in our work today is to develop creative, free thinking skills, the need for independent learning and skills. When talking to foreigners who have experience in communicating with Uzbek youth, we tried to find out their opinions and opinions about our work. Foreigners emphasize that our young people are more motivated, hardworking, have a wide range of knowledge, and recognize that it is better if they pay more attention to the formation of creative, free thinking, practical application of knowledge, independent learning needs and skills. A study of the literature in this field and real-life observations show that today new methods of teaching foreign languages, the practical application of their modern technologies is a modern requirement.

According to experts, a loving attitude to the child in the family, giving them enough freedom, more communication, especially the development of creative talent and thinking, has a positive effect on the formation of independent thinking. The relevance of the educational process to the development of creative abilities in the work requires the democratization of relations between teachers and students in all educational institutions (kindergarten, school, lyceum, college, university), the teacher's position, the introduction of new approaches to education, form, content and technology. Reaches. Our esteemed President Sh.M.Mirzиеv states that "Our main goal is to ensure that young people have access to quality education, to create all the necessary conditions for them to realize their abilities and talents" [2].

It is no secret that even today, in most cases, the school process is dominated by the teacher, who is mainly the transmitter of knowledge, information and behavior. they behave as expressors of their opinions, advice, and instructions. Such a situation is not conducive to the development of creative, free-thinking skills in learners, but to

their passive assimilation of the stock of ready-made knowledge, the formation in them of obligatory obedience. Existing forms of education and traditional teaching technologies rely mainly on teacher activism. A new approach to education, which needs to be introduced in the future, innovative educational technologies should be based on the activity of more learners, aimed at forming in them the need and skills for independent learning. The teacher should move from the role of a transmitter to the role of a developer, forming a process of active learning of students, psychologically and pedagogically rationally supporting their existing needs for knowledge, free thinking, creativity, innovation. It is natural that the introduction of new educational technologies and advanced pedagogical innovations in educational practice will not happen by itself.

In our view, there is a need for a scientific approach to the introduction of pedagogical innovations and an in-depth study of the factors influencing this process. As a prelude to this work, we can cite the following views expressed in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

Consistent measures are being taken to raise the education system to a new level, to improve the quality of teacher training on the basis of advanced international standards and to increase the level of coverage with higher pedagogical education. In particular, the increase in the coverage of preschool education, 11 years overall

In order to meet the growing demand for highly qualified specialists in connection with the introduction of the secondary education system and the expansion of higher education, 1 foreign and 4 local higher education institutions specializing in teacher training have been established in recent years ta'lim Joint educational programs with countries have been established. Our research results show that the successful implementation of pedagogical innovations in the community and the intended effectiveness depends on a number of factors. They can be divided into three major groups:

1. Factors related to the characteristics of the proposed pedagogical technology, taking into account the natural needs and interests of students in language acquisition:

2. Taking into account the emergence, development, introduction of pedagogical technology, the provision of sufficient information about it, the introduction of step-by-step or non-implementation, the material and financial support for the introduction of pedagogical technology:

3. Factors related to the socio-psychological characteristics of the people involved in the introduction of pedagogical technology and the pedagogical community, and tasks such as their gradual implementation in practice in accordance with the requirements of today's world. The Law on Education, adopted for the development of this sector, should be taken as an example and put into practice the National Program of Personnel Training. Based on research and experience, innovative personnel with high potential can be seen as a result of the introduction of pedagogical technologies. In conclusion, conducting the educational process in

coordination with modern innovative technologies will ensure the speed of the student's acceptance of activity in the learning process. Today's era requires a teacher not only to be a master of his profession, but also a good psychologist, knowledgeable in all areas of interest to the student, one of the first to be aware of modern technology and innovations in the world, able to communicate fluently in one of the foreign languages. [3]

In order to effectively introduce pedagogical technology, it is necessary to provide members of the pedagogical team with the necessary information about this innovation and to determine their attitude to this pedagogical technology, on this basis, to take measures to improve this attitude. On this basis, significant work is being done to strengthen the civic position and activity of our working generation, to educate them to think independently, to acquire modern knowledge and skills, to compete in the international arena. Most importantly, the task of constant communication with young people, ensuring their employment, finding their place in life, becoming worthy members of society, improving working and living conditions should become the criterion of our daily activities.

REFERENCES:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг Олий Мажлисга мурожаатномаси.
2. Мирзиёев Ш.М. —Халқимизнинг розилиги бизнинг фаолиятимизга берилган энг олий баҳодир».
3. Костикова. М.Н. Инновационные процессы в развитии педагогического образования // Сб.: Традиции и инновации в системе образования. Мат. науч-прак. конф. Ч.1. –Чита: Изд-во ЗабГПУ, 2014